

ITER-relevant Irradiation Head of KATANA Water Activation Loop at JSI TRIGA Reactor

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ABSTRACT

The KATANA water activation facility, designed as a high-energy gamma and neutron source, was successfully commissioned at the JSI TRIGA reactor in late 2023. Since then, several experimental campaigns have been conducted to evaluate its operational behaviour, establishing a solid foundation for future benchmarking studies. Although the current configuration of KATANA, particularly the inner irradiation head, does not yet replicate the exact conditions expected in the ITER cooling system, it serves as a simplified test environment for device characterisation. To better reproduce ITER-relevant conditions, the development of a new irradiation head is under investigation for a future operating phase of the KATANA loop. The objective of this new design is to mimic the behaviour of water within an ITER First Wall panel. Ideally, the new irradiation head would either emphasise the dominant effect of a heterogeneous activation function over fluid-dynamic effects or combine both effects in the same sense, thereby avoiding their mutual cancellation. The proposed modular design shows promising feasibility but requires further detailed neutronic and computational fluid dynamics-based analyses before prototype fabrication and experimental validation.

Keywords: Water activation, KATANA, ITER, fusion

1. INTRODUCTION

Water, as the primary coolant in fusion reactors, plays a crucial role in radiation safety and shielding due to its activation under neutron irradiation. Upon exposure, oxygen in water undergoes nuclear reactions that produce short-lived radionuclides such as ^{16}N , ^{17}N , and ^{19}O . These decay rapidly, emitting high-energy gamma rays and neutrons. In particular, the $^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$ reaction, with a threshold energy of approximately 10.5 MeV, leads to significantly elevated activity levels in fusion systems - up to five orders of magnitude higher than in comparable fission reactors [1].

To support ITER [2], DEMO and other future water-cooled fusion reactors, the KATANA irradiation facility [3, 4, 5] was designed, constructed, and commissioned at the end of 2023 at the JSI TRIGA research reactor in Slovenia [6]. Utilising a closed-loop water activation system, KATANA provides a stable and well-characterised high-energy radiation field (6 MeV–7 MeV γ , ~ 1 MeV neutrons) [7]. Its design enables a broad range of water activation-based experiments, including shielding experiments with ITER-relevant materials, detector response studies, short-lived moving source tracking, integral cross-section measurements, and spectrum and dose rate assessments. Ultimately, KATANA aims to facilitate benchmark-quality experiments to validate advanced fluid activation codes (such as Radio-Species Transport (RSTM) code [8, 9], FLUNED [10, 11], GammaFlow and ActiFlow [12]) and to establish itself as a reference facility for the calibration of high-energy γ detectors [13].

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The aim of this paper is to present a conceptual design of a new ITER-relevant irradiation head for KATANA, which mimics conditions relevant to those in the ITER Normal Heat Flux First Wall (NHF FW) panel.

2. KATANA WATER ACTIVATION LOOP

The short-term activation of water consists primarily of the activation of oxygen isotopes by the reactions $^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$, $^{17}\text{O}(n,p)^{17}\text{N}$ and $^{18}\text{O}(n,\gamma)^{19}\text{O}$ [14], with a very small contribution from the activation of dissolved gases, corrosion products and additives. Activated nitrogen and oxygen nuclides subsequently decay, releasing γ rays and neutrons with different energies. The (n,p) reactions on ^{16}O and ^{17}O are threshold reactions, while the (n, γ) reaction on ^{18}O already occurs at thermal energies. The most important water activation reactions and the corresponding decay properties are listed in Table I. The main contribution to the activity of water during operation is the activated isotope ^{16}N due to the high natural abundance of the isotope ^{16}O and high cross-section for the (n,p) reaction.

Table I. Activation products of water [14].

Reaction	$t_{1/2}$ [s]	Major decay products	Threshold energy	Natural abundance
$^{16}\text{O}(n,p)^{16}\text{N}$	7.13	γ : 6.129 MeV (67 %)	~ 10.5 MeV	99.76 %
		γ : 7.115 MeV (5 %)		
		n : 0.383 MeV (35 %)		
$^{17}\text{O}(n,p)^{17}\text{N}$	4.17	γ : 0.871 MeV (3 %)	~ 9 MeV	0.04 %
		n : 1.171 MeV (53 %)		
		n : 1.700 MeV (7 %)		
		γ : 0.110 MeV (3 %)		
$^{18}\text{O}(n,\text{fl})^{19}\text{O}$	26.88	γ : 0.197 MeV (96 %)	< 1 eV	0.2 %
		γ : 1.357 MeV (50 %)		
		γ : 1.444 MeV (3 %)		

2.1. KATANA irradiation facility

The KATANA water circuit, which is shown schematically in Figure 1, consists of a pipe loop that is partially inserted into the Radial Piercing Port (RPP). The main components are the inner irradiation Snail, two outer observation Snails and transport pipes. All important components, sensors and instruments for controlling and operating the circuit, e.g. pump, valves, Coriolis flow metre, temperature and pressure sensors, etc., are located outside the RPP (shown in black). A three-way valve can be used to fully or partially adjust the water distribution between the primary loop (shown in red) and the secondary loop (shown in blue), which are referred to as Configuration 1 and Configuration 2, respectively, in the rest of the text. The primary loop is designed for the fastest possible transport of activated water in order to achieve a high total activity of ^{16}N and ^{17}N within the outer observation part (i.e. Snail No. 1), which leads to a lower experimental uncertainty, e.g. for performing shielding experiments with ITER-relevant materials. The secondary loop (or so-called delay loop) extends the travel time of the activated water and favours a $^{16}\text{N}/^{19}\text{O}$ isotope ratio in favour of ^{19}O . The use of these two different circuit components, each optimised for its specific function, improves the overall performance and accuracy of the system. In addition, the loop branching also enables the investigation of more complex scenarios such as the simulation of the mixing of the activated water flow from different pipes and/or the investigation of leakage scenarios.

To minimise occupational radiation exposure inside the reactor hall, two special γ & neutron shielding plugs are used inside the RPP together with a 40 cm thick and 180 cm high concrete wall around the experimental area. The entire KATANA is controlled and monitored via the control panel, located

Figure 1. A schematic of the KATANA water circuit (left) and constructed & commissioned KATANA facility (figure adapted from [4]).

outside of the labyrinth-shaped concrete wall. A fully constructed and commissioned KATANA facility is shown in Figure 1 on the right.

3. COMPARISON BETWEEN SIMPLIFIED AND DETAILED ACTIVATION MODEL

The Radio-Species Transport Model (RSTM) method is a simulation methodology developed by Fusion for Energy based on the Ansys Fluent® user-defined scalar approach. It predicts the activation of a flowing fluid in domains where neutron fields and flow regimes require the coupling of activation and fluid dynamic effects [8].

A first insight of the comparison between the simplified conventional analytical method (which simplifies the problem by assuming uniform velocity profile and homogeneity of neutron field within volumes) and the application of the RSTM code (which integrates the fluid dynamics and neutron activation effects using a computational fluid dynamic (CFD)-based methodology) to the KATANA water activation loop has been performed [9] and is briefly presented here. Specifically, only the Inner Irradiation Snail head (Inner Snail) and Outer Observation Snail head (Outer Snail), both shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 on the left.

The ratio C/C' (C = conventional, C' = RSTM) represents a relative comparison between the two methods, where both C and C' are initially expressed as radioisotope specific activity, i.e., radioisotope activity concentration (Bq/cm^3) at the outlet of the Snail head as a function of mass-flow rate. The resulting C/C' curves for the Inner Snail and the Outer Snail are shown in Figure 2, above and below, respectively. In Inner Snail, fluid-dynamic effects, counterbalanced by the opposite influence of the activation function, lead to minimal differences between the RSTM and the conventional methods, resulting in a flat C/C' curve. In contrast, Outer Snail shows fluid-dynamic effects due to the absence of the activation function (decay-only), resulting in a more irregular C/C' curve, especially at lower mass flow rates. In addition, nuclides with longer half-lives in Outer Snail show a lower sensitivity to fluid-dynamic effects.

Under conditions where fluid-dynamic effects are less significant, such as at higher mass flow rates, both methods provide similar predictions. This similarity is particularly evident in the decay-only

scenario, since in the presence of the neutron field the results of the conventional method and the RSTM converge due to an unexpected counterbalancing effect.

Figure 2. Relative comparison of the simplified (conventional) and the detailed (RSTM) activation model of radioisotope specific activity: C/C' values at the outlet of the Inner Irradiation Snail Head (top) and the Outer Observation Snail Head (bottom) for the most important water activation nuclides: ^{16}N , ^{17}N and ^{19}O . Figure taken from [9].

Based on these results, an alternative ITER-relevant irradiation head for a future phase of the KATANA loop is investigated. The aim of this design is to replicate the behaviour of water within an ITER NHF FW panel. Ideally, the new irradiation head should either enhance the dominant influence of the heterogeneous activation function over fluid-dynamic effects, or ensure that both effects act synergistically rather than counteracting each other.

4. ITER-RELEVANT IRRADIATION HEAD

The final design of the KATANA closed-water loop [4] for the first experimental phase [15, 7] aimed at achieving a high water activity inside the outer observation Snail, leading to a consistent and stable production of high-energy γ rays and neutrons. Such a well-defined irradiation facility enables various

benchmark experiments based on water activation, which also target the shielding studies of the ITER-relevant materials. In addition, the complexity of the circuit, in particular the design of the inner and outer Snail, has been designed to ensure a relatively uniform/smooth water profile along the circuit and to minimise CFD effects such as stagnation points. In this way, the codes for computational fluid activation can be applied with ease and higher precision.

In the future, the KATANA will focus on performing experiments more relevant to ITER cooling systems and on validating general-purpose fluid activation tools also in a more complex scenario. The aim is to approach conditions closer to the breakdown of the conventional (i.e. non-CFD) method assumptions and, if possible, to match ITER cooling systems. Therefore, in the framework of the EUROfusion project WP PrIO, in which several EUROfusion partners are involved, a new design of the inner irradiation part is being investigated, addressing conditions more relevant to ITER. In particular, in collaboration with F4E, an alternative design of the inner irradiation head is being investigated, targeting the key features of an ITER FW module [8] (see Figure 3 on the left). Despite the challenges posed by the complexity of FW hydraulic routing and the limited size of the JSI TRIGA RPP, a compromise approach was explored. This design strategy:

- preserves the hydraulic features (inlet and outlet pipework, waterboxes and fingers),
- preserves the residence time (by adjustment of the flow rate whilst also preserving the fluid regime according to the Reynolds number, and
- preserves the orientation of neutron flux gradients

of the NHF kind of the FW (mean residence time: 11.9 s, Re : 17310, velocity: 0.79 m/s, volume: 55 L, flow rate: 4.7 L/s]. However, it deviates from replicating some complicated features such as the arrangement of multiple fingers. Several conceptual designs based on the spiral disk (SD) concept are currently under investigation (the latest one is shown in Figure 3 middle). These designs have common criteria, including the use of one or more SDs, water boxes, channels and interconnecting pipes. The sizes of these elements are adjusted so that the volume ratio corresponds to that of an FW, with the diameters of the SDs and water boxes optimised to match the dimensions of the RPP and maximise the water volume.

Figure 3. ITER normal heat flux first wall complete cooling circuit (left: adaptation from [8]), latest solid disc-based conceptual design (only water boxes) for the new ITER-relevant irradiation head (middle) and current inner irradiation Snail (right).

The design was gradually improved over the course of 2024, but some crucial findings slowed down the finalisation of the process considerably. It turned out that the complex ITER-relevant head cannot be manufactured using the same approach as the current Snail-head. The main problems are the limitations of 3D printing, i.e. avoidance of support structures (angle below 45° from the top), and extraction of leftover powder (closed geometry). It turned out that the 3D printing option is unsuitable for such spiral disc designs. To keep the desired geometry of the ITER-relevant head as close to the optimum as possible (mimic ITER-FW), a standard technique of using a CNC machine was proposed to produce each spiral disc (green) and gaskets (red) separately and to connect (tighten) them together using bolts (black) as in the figure below. The full schematic of the latest design of the ITER-relevant head is shown

in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Schematic of the latest design of the ITER-relevant irradiation head (+ exploded view).

The switch from 3D printing to manual production has had a major impact on the optimisation process and has meant that the final design of the ITER-relevant head is not yet complete. Prior to manufacturing the prototype, a series of calculations must be re-performed to obtain the necessary confirmation that the proposed design correctly reproduces/mimics the desired ITER-relevant conditions:

- calculations of the new reaction rate (RR) distributions along the new ITER-relevant head (the proposed design is very different from the Snail-head) (shown in Figure 5)
- followed by detailed CFD-based activity calculations along the KATANA circuit
- calculation of residence time distribution along the head to match ITER FW module characteristics

The reaction rate (RR) values were calculated using MCNP [16] on a detailed rectangular mesh tally with 7938 voxels ($21 \times 21 \times 18$) with a side of ~ 1 cm, which completely covered the entire water area of the ITER-relevant head. RR values were calculated throughout the entire region of interest (ITER-relevant head) in the approximation of the whole geometry consisting only of the target oxygen isotopes (^{16}O , ^{17}O or ^{18}O) rather than the actual present material. Such a procedure is commonly used as only voxels that coincide with the exact water volume are at a further stage taken into account for coupled neutronic and CFD codes. In addition, the rectangular mesh was used instead of a cylindrical mesh as it is easier to implement in the CFD codes. The calculated RR values, given as reactions per cubic centimetre per second, for the generated isotopes ^{16}N , ^{17}N and ^{19}O are shown in Figure 5 representing a mesh tally along the region of interest. The highest values are naturally obtained for ^{16}N , which is due to the highest natural abundance of ^{16}O isotope and the high cross-section values and are in the first centimetre of water $\sim 5700\times$ and $\sim 12\times$ higher than for ^{17}N and ^{19}O , respectively. As the RPP and therefore the inner Snail is located ~ 11 cm below the centre of the reactor core, the RR values in the upper part are consistently slightly higher than in the lower part.

Figure 5. Reaction rate profiles for the generated isotopes ^{16}N , ^{17}N and ^{19}O , calculated along the region of interest (ITER-relevant head). RR values are normalised to the full reactor power of 250 kW.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The KATANA facility has demonstrated stable operation and high reproducibility of activation fields, providing a robust platform for benchmarking water activation under fusion-relevant conditions. Building on this foundation, a new ITER-relevant irradiation head is being developed to reproduce the coupled effects of neutron activation and coolant flow representative of the ITER First Wall. While the current inner irradiation Snail head was successfully manufactured using metal 3D printing, the complexity of the ITER-relevant head geometry makes this manufacturing approach impractical. Therefore, a manually assembled CNC-machined modular design has been adopted. This approach introduces additional simplifications, and the resulting configuration may deviate from the idealised “on-paper” design. The main parameter used to assess such deviations is the residence-time distribution, which will be evaluated through detailed neutronic and CFD-based RSTM analyses.

Modification of the loop to better reproduce ITER conditions, i.e. the replacement of the inner irradiation Snail with the ITER-relevant head and potential redesign of the secondary loop, is anticipated for 2027, followed by a new experimental campaign.

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